

Highly responsive flexible photodetectors based on MOVPE grown uniform few-layer MoS₂

Daniel S. Schneider^{1,2}, Annika Grundmann³, Andreas Bablich⁴, Vikram Passi^{1,5},
Satender Kataria², Holger Kalisch³, Michael Heuken^{3,6}, Andrei Vescan³, Daniel Neumaier^{1,7},
Max C. Lemme^{1,2}

¹AMO GmbH, Advanced Microelectronic Center Aachen (AMICA), Otto-Blumenthal-Str.
25, 52074 Aachen, Germany

²RWTH Aachen University, Chair of Electronic Devices, Otto-Blumenthal-Str. 2, 52074
Aachen, Germany

³RWTH Aachen University, Compound Semiconductor Technology, Sommerfeldstr. 18,
52074 Aachen, Germany

⁴University of Siegen, School of Science and Technology, Hölderlinstr. 3, 57076 Siegen,
Germany

⁵Raith B.V., De Dintel 27A, 5684 PS Best, The Netherlands

⁶AIXTRON SE, Dornkaulstr. 2, 52134 Herzogenrath, Germany

⁷University of Wuppertal, 42285 Wuppertal, Germany

Corresponding author: Email: lemme@amo.de / Phone: (+49) 241 8867 201

Abstract

Two-dimensional (2D) transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) are seen as promising candidates for flexible electronic and optoelectronic devices due to their high tensile strength and favorable optical properties. Molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) is a benchmark material for TMDCs, which has already been studied extensively. Here, we report on highly responsive flexible few-layer MoS_2 photodetectors based on MoS_2 synthesized uniformly for full coverage of 2 inch sapphire wafers using metalorganic vapor-phase epitaxy (MOVPE). Device performance is studied by electro-optical characterization. Electrostatic gating allows tuning both the responsivity between 150 A / W and 920 A / W and the specific detectivity between almost 10^{12} Jones and 10^{10} Jones. The measured spectrally resolved responsivities of the detectors suggest applications in the blue-light range, with opportunities for finetuning the most sensitive wavelength through gating, as shown through optical simulations. Finally, the flexible devices were bent to demonstrate their suitability for flexible electronics in fields of future internet of things and medical devices.

Keywords: MoS_2 ; transition metal dichalcogenides; photodetector; flexible; metal organic vapor phase epitaxy

Two-dimensional (2D) materials, in particular semiconducting transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs), are promising candidates for next-generation electronic and optoelectronic devices. Monolayers of molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) employed as channel material in ultra-thin transistors showed on/off ratios of more than 10^8 ¹ and comparably high electron mobility of almost $200 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ ², in particular considering their thickness of just three atomic planes. MoS_2 has also received significant attention for optoelectronic devices due to its thickness-dependent bandgap ^{3,4} and high optical absorption even in the monolayer regime ⁵. Moreover, monolayer MoS_2 can withstand mechanical strains up to 11% ⁶ which renders this material suitable for flexible electronic devices. Several kinds of TMDC-based photodetectors have been demonstrated already. Complex heterostructures with MoS_2 light absorbing layers ⁷⁻⁹ and phototransistors can achieve ultra-high responsivities in the range of hundreds of A/W ¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Recently, MoS_2 photodetectors have been integrated into a photonic platform ¹⁵. However, most of the TMDC-based optoelectronic devices have been assembled using small flakes exfoliated from crystals and transferred on target substrates, a process which is not compatible with industrial manufacturing ¹⁶. The increasing demand for photodetectors in applications, e.g. for the automotive industry, for the Internet of Things (IoT), for smart wearables ^{17,18} and in the biomedical sector ^{19,20}, require cost-efficient, stable and reliable fabrication of high-performance photodetectors.

Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) in principle addresses the issue of large-scale TMDC growth, but preserving and scaling the high quality of micrometer-sized CVD single crystals ²¹ to relevant wafer sizes is still challenging ^{22,23}. Thermally activated conversion (TAC) is based on metal films that are e.g. sulfurized to form large area 2D films. The TAC process requires very high homogeneity of the sputtered or evaporated metal film²⁴ and

bears the risk of unsulfurized regions for thicker films. CVD and TAC films may have nanocrystalline character^{25,26} or a vertical layer orientation²⁷. Metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) can overcome these issues by providing superior reproducibility, film homogeneity and scalability which is required for electronic devices, as shown for the growth of TMDCs like WS₂²⁸ and MoS₂²⁹.

In this work, we demonstrate high-responsivity metal-semiconductor-metal (MSM) photodetectors with gate-tunable sensitivity based on few-layer (FL) MoS₂. The devices are based on high-quality large-scale MoS₂, grown by MOVPE on sapphire³⁰ and transferred onto flexible polyimide (PI) substrates for device fabrication.

Results and Discussion

The material properties of MOVPE FL-MoS₂ have been examined in detail, both, on its growth substrate sapphire and after being transferred onto 90 nm silicon oxide on silicon substrates. This serves to evaluate the impact of film handling and transfer. We performed confocal Raman measurements with a laser wavelength of 532 nm and a power of 1 mW on the reference (i.e. as-grown) and transferred MoS₂ layers. The Raman spectra of the MoS₂ films before and after transfer show identical positions of the A_{1g} Raman mode at 406 cm⁻¹ and the E_{2g} mode at 383 cm⁻¹ (Figure 1a). This indicates that the quality of MoS₂ did not change significantly during the transfer process.

Figure 1: (a) Raman spectra with the A_{1g} and E_{2g} modes of the as-grown MOVPE-MoS₂ film on sapphire substrate and after transfer onto Si/SiO₂. (b) Photoluminescence (PL) measurements with a strong excitonic A peak, indicating a pronouncedly photoactive material. (c) AFM measurement of the MoS₂ layers including height profile before transfer. Inset: magnification of area highlighted by the blue box.

The difference of around 23 cm^{-1} between the A_{1g} and the E_{2g} modes indicates a thickness of approximately 3 - 4 layers for the FL-MoS₂ film⁴. The films have been further analyzed by photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy, which is a well-suited technique for characterizing 2D materials. The measurement in Figure 1b demonstrates a photoactive layer with the presence of both A and B excitonic peaks around 1.83 eV and 1.96 eV, respectively³¹. Although the B peak is slightly quenched after the transfer to Si/SiO₂, it can still be detected. The quenching may be caused by substrate-induced interference³². The appearance of both excitonic peaks A and B proves FL properties of the MoS₂ epilayer as these features would disappear for a higher number of MoS₂ sheets or bulk MoS₂^{31,33}. We carefully scratched the grown MoS₂ layer with tweezers and measured the step height by atomic force microscopy (AFM) (Figure 1c, inset). The measured step of approximately 2.6 nm confirms the presence of 3 - 4 layers of MoS₂^{31,34} as derived from

Raman measurements. The surface morphology of the transferred MoS₂ film is shown in the blue box of Figure 1c. The isolated grains of MoS₂ indicate that the topmost monolayer consists of isolated islands and thus explains a relatively high measured average film roughness of 1 nm.”

The flexible MoS₂ devices (Figure 2a) have been analyzed electro-optically with a semiconductor analyzer in a multi-probe station and wavelength-dependent photocurrents have been measured using a customized spectral response measurement set-up^{35,36}.

Self-aligned nickel edge drain and source contacts to the MoS₂ active regions have been manufactured, similar to those on graphene devices³⁷. This has been shown to improve the interface between contact metals and TMDC channels, thereby reducing the contact resistance^{38,39}. The optical micrograph in Figure 2b shows a single device with interdigitated metal contacts. Each photodetector device consists of 48 parallel channels, each with a length of 5 μm and a width of 70 μm. The schematic cross-section of an MSM back-gated MoS₂ photodetector with a 5 μm long channel between the Ni drain and source electrodes is shown in Figure 2c.

Figure 2: (a) Photograph of the MOVPE-MoS₂ photodetectors on flexible polyimide substrate. (b) Microscope image of a single device (c) Schematic cross-section of the complete device. (d) Transfer characteristics in the dark and under illumination for $V_{ds} = 1\text{ V}$ and $L_{ch} = 5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in logarithmic (left) and linear (right) current scale. (e) Photocurrent (solid lines) and dark current (dashed lines) of the flexible MSM photodetector for $V_{gs} = -2\text{ V}$ and 0 V .

First, we demonstrate the n-type metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistor operation of our MoS₂ devices. The transfer characteristics both in linear (right) and log scale (left) are shown in the dark (dashed line) in Figure 2d. At a drain-source voltage of $V_{ds} = 1\text{ V}$, we observe an ON/OFF ratio of about 10^6 , with an OFF current of the order of

10^{-10} A and an ON current of the order of 10^{-4} A. This is on par with reported values of field effect transistors fabricated on small-area mechanically exfoliated and CVD films^{40–42}, demonstrating the excellent electronic quality of the MOVPE MoS₂ films. The horizontal shift of the transfer curve under illumination (Figure 2d) indicates a photogating effect, which is caused by trapped charge carriers^{43–45}.

The field effect mobility μ has been extracted from the drain current in the linear regime in the dark in Figure 2d with equation (1)

$$\mu = \frac{L \cdot g_m}{W \cdot C_{ox} \cdot V_{ds}}, \quad (1)$$

where L is the channel length, W the channel width, C_{ox} the gate oxide capacitance, V_{ds} the drain-source and g_m the transconductance $\frac{dI_d}{dV_{gs}}$, which further includes the gate-source voltage V_{gs}. The estimated extrinsic field effect mobility is $\mu \sim 3$ cm²/Vs for a device with 5 μ m channel length and 35 nm Al₂O₃ back gate oxide (dielectric constant $\epsilon = 9$). This is not an accurate value because the extracted mobility is influenced by the presence of considerable contact resistances between the metal and the channel material, as is the case here^{46,47}.

Under dark condition, the current is lowest at negative V_{gs}, when the channel is depleted of charge carriers. This suggests that the performance of the MSMs can be tuned by choosing a suitable gate voltage to minimize the dark current. A lower dark current has several advantages: lower light detection levels due to noise reduction and detectors consuming lower stand-by power. This is particularly important for the application as image sensor arrays with up to millions of individual photodetectors, for low-power consumer electronics in the fields of smart wearables and IoT applications.

The output characteristics (drain current I_d versus drain-source voltage V_{ds}) of the MSM under 1 mW/cm^2 white-light illumination (solid line) is shown in Figure 2d. The back-gate contact in the MSM photodetectors allows tuning the dark current I_{dark} , which is reduced by a factor of $\sim 10^3$, from 837 nA to 768 pA , by depleting the transistor channel from $V_{gs} = 0 \text{ V}$ to -2 V (dashed lines in Figure 2e). The corresponding photocurrents $I_{photo} = I_{illuminated} - I_{dark}$ measured under 1 mW/cm^2 of white-LED illumination show an improvement in the dynamic range DR, defined as $20 \cdot \log(I_{photo} / I_{dark})$, from 33 dB at $V_{gs} = 0 \text{ V}$ to 83 dB at $V_{gs} = -2 \text{ V}$, enabled through gate voltage tuning.

Figure 3: Schematic band diagrams of the MSM photodetector in (a) dark and (b) under illumination for negative and positive V_{gs} . All plots show energy as a function of position x along the channel.

The related band diagrams of the biased MSM photodetectors in dark are shown in Figure 3a. By applying a negative gate voltage, the barrier height Φ_B of the Ni contacts to MoS₂ (~ 150 meV⁴⁸) is increased for charge carriers, and the n-type channel is also depleted. Therefore, the dark current is suppressed. For positive gate voltages, the barrier for electrons is significantly lowered so that electrons can be injected into the channel, where electrons form an inversion channel, while the barrier for holes is still very large. The combination of the inversion channel and the low barrier for electrons leads to a high dark current. Figure 3b presents the illuminated Ni-contacted MoS₂ channel. Again, a negative gate voltage increases the barrier for electrons, while photo-generated electron-hole pairs in MoS₂ can be extracted by the lateral electrical field. In summary, the photocurrent can be increased by applying a positive gate voltage, which increases also the dark current. A trade-off between high photocurrent and low dark current is therefore inherent.

Moreover, we have investigated the dependence of the photocurrent on the optical power density up to 6 mW / cm², the maximum of the employed light source (Figure 4a). Compared to Park et al., who describe a strong nonlinearity in the device response on the optical power density up to 10 mW / cm²⁴⁹, we observe an almost linear dependence for illumination up to 6 mW / cm².

Figure 4: (a) Optical-power-dependent photocurrent at $V_{gs} = -4$ V and $V_{ds} = 1$ V. b) Gate voltage (V_{gs}) dependent responsivities (c) and specific detectivities for a white-light intensity of $P_{illumination} = 1$ mW / cm². (d) Transient characteristics of a MoS₂ photodetector. (e) Rise and (f) decay time extraction of the time-resolved curves.

We characterized the detectors in the linear regime while illuminating with optical power densities of 1 mW/cm² and low bias voltages, as required by low-power devices. One key figure of merit of photodetectors is their responsivity R , which can be calculated by equation (2)

$$R = \frac{I_{photo}}{P_{illumination} \cdot A_{MoS2}}, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{illumination}$ is the illumination power density and A_{MoS2} the active area of the photodetector. A maximum responsivity R of 540 A/W ($V_{ds} = 2$ V) was reached at $V_{gs} = 0$ V, while a negative gate voltage of $V_{gs} = -2$ V reduces the responsivity to 150 A/W (Figure 4b). Positive gate voltages induce electrons in the channel and therefore lead to

higher R up to 920 A/W at $V_{gs} = 4V$. This high responsivity can be explained by the photogain due to the photoconductive effect that dominates the behavior ^{44,50}, which has also been observed in other FL MoS₂ photodetector structures ^{49,51,52}.

A second figure of merit for photodetectors is their specific detectivity D^* , which describes the capabilities to capture weak signals and can be calculated using the equation (3) with the assumption, that shot noise generated by the dark current is dominating ⁵³.

$$D^* = \frac{R \cdot \sqrt{A_{MoS_2}}}{\sqrt{2 \cdot q \cdot I_{dark}}} \quad (3)$$

Here, q is the elementary charge. By electrostatic gating, a maximum specific detectivity close to 10^{12} Jones was achieved at $V_{gs} = -2V$ which decreases to approximately 10^{10} Jones at positive V_{gs} . A positive gate voltage effectively lowers the metal-MoS₂ Schottky barrier, which leads to higher drain currents at a given V_{ds} . This increases the dark current and therefore limits the specific detectivity. At negative gate bias, the devices show detectivities of more than one order of magnitude higher than detectors based on FL-MoS₂ flakes ^{49,51,52,54}.

Time-resolved measurements have been performed under modulated white-light illumination of 1 mW cm². Figure 4d shows the dynamics with a current rise time (current 10% to 90%) of ~0.5 s (Figure 4e) and a slow decay (current 90% to 10%) that does not saturate even within one second (Figure 4f). This slow and non-saturating response may be explained by the nanocrystalline structure of the MOVPE films with grain sizes around 100 nm (see Figure 1 (c) inset). Defects at grain boundaries, interface states at the Al₂O₃ / MoS₂ interface, charge traps in the Al₂O₃, sulfur vacancies and OH⁻ ions in the MoS₂ layer ^{55–58} can lead to a persistent photogating effect that manifests in slow recombination

times⁵⁹. The photoresponse may be further enhanced by improving the material quality, including larger grain sizes, proper encapsulation¹³ or functionalization⁶⁰, by improving the MoS₂/oxide interface in order to reduce interface trap states or by the use of a ferroelectric induced local electrostatic field^{45,61}.

Figure 5: (a) Measured and simulated wavelength-dependent responsivity of MoS₂. (b) Optical simulations of the absorption of MSM photodetectors with increasing number of MoS₂ layers. (c) Comparison of photocurrent and dark current for $V_{gs} = -2$ V before and after 100 bending cycles.

We further characterized the spectrally resolved response of the photodetectors. Three prominent peaks were observed in the spectra (Figure 5a). The two peaks in the range from 600 nm to 700 nm (2 eV to 1.7 eV) are related to the direct band gap transitions in MoS₂, i.e. the B exciton at 615 nm (2.02 eV) and the A exciton at 650 nm (1.91 eV),^{3,62}. However, a much stronger peak is observed in the blue region of the spectrum, around 425 nm (2.92 eV). This peak can be assigned to the C exciton, and its distinct strength can be attributed to band nesting effects in MoS₂^{62,63}. The high sensitivity in the blue wavelength range of the detector makes it particularly interesting for the detection and assessment of blue-light hazards⁶⁴. These experimental data have been validated using

optical simulations based on the transfer-matrix method ⁶⁵ of the same device stack configuration (Figure 5a) with optical parameters of MoS₂ ⁶⁶. Furthermore, we used the model to explore the design space for our detectors by increasing the number of MoS₂ layers (Figure 5b). We predict that we can shift the maximum responsivity towards higher wavelengths (from 440 nm to 570 nm) by adding additional MoS₂ layers, i.e. by tuning the band structure through 2D layer stacking. This approach can be used to design detectors according to spectral requirements of prospective applications by growing the exact layer number. The MOVPE technique, which allows controlled growth of TMDC layers, is suitable for this purpose. In previous studies, process parameters such as precursor flows, chamber pressure and substrate temperature have already been optimized ^{28–30}.

The mechanical stability of the flexible photodetectors has been investigated by bending (tensile strain) to a defined radius of 25 mm and by measuring currents before and after each bending cycle. The initial dark current measured in the pristine, unbent condition is in the nA range, and is very similar to the dark current measured after 100 bending cycles. The same behavior is observed for the photocurrent, which remains in the μ A range after 100 bending cycles (Figure 5c). This experiment confirms that the detectors withstand 100 cycles of 0.25% tensile strain (maximum strain defined by the setup). The potential weak spot, the ALD Al₂O₃ oxide, obviously did not crack or break down electrically. This is in line with previous observations by Choi et al., who showed that ALD Al₂O₃ films of <50 nm can withstand up to 1% of strain ⁶⁷. The detectors should therefore be applicable in the medical sector, smart-wearable technology and also for consumer IoT products with curved shapes.

Conclusion

In summary we have demonstrated a scalable manufacturing process for flexible metal-semiconductor-metal photodetectors based on few-layer MOVPE-MoS₂. The quality of the wafer scale MOVPE-MoS₂ is confirmed through field effect transistors with mobilities up to 3 cm² / Vs and high ON/OFF current ratios of six orders of magnitude. The flexible photodetectors can be tuned either for high responsivity or high specific detectivity by electrostatic gating. They reach dynamic ranges up to 83 dB under 1 mW/cm² white-light illumination, a responsivity of 150 A / W and a high specific detectivity of 10¹² Jones at V_{ds} = 2 V and V_{gs} = -2 V. Changing the gate voltage to V_{gs} = 4 V allows operating the detector with R = 920 A / W at the same V_{ds} = 2 V, although consequently at a reduced D* of 10¹⁰ Jones. Spectrally resolved measurements qualify the devices for highly responsive blue light hazard detection at 425 nm, which is confirmed through modeling. We further predict that the maximum responsivity can be tuned by over 100 nm through adding additional layers of MoS₂. Our scalable approach could enable future optical sensors that favor bendable and ultra-thin electronics, for example in the medical field.

Experimental methods

MOVPE of few-layer MoS₂

Highly uniform FL-MoS₂ has been epitaxially grown in a commercial AIXTRON Planetary Reactor in 10 x 2" configuration on sapphire (0001) substrates. First, a substrate prebake at 1050°C in pure H₂ atmosphere has been performed to promote lateral growth by avoiding the formation of a parasitic carbonaceous film ²⁹. Afterwards, growth has been carried out at a substrate temperature of 845°C with nitrogen as carrier gas and a pressure of 30 hPa. A high sulfur to molybdenum ratio of 200,000 has been chosen to achieve homogeneous FL MoS₂ films on wafer scale. To achieve this, the precursor flows have been set to 0.1 nmol/min for molybdenum hexacarbonyl (MCO) and 20 μmol/min for di-ter-butyl-sulfide (DTBS).

Device Fabrication

Back-gated MSM structures have been fabricated on flexible polyimide (PI) substrates by sputtering 50 nm thick aluminum gate electrodes defined by means of contact lithography and lift-off, followed by atomic layer deposition of 35 nm Al₂O₃. Subsequently, the FL-MoS₂ film has been transferred from sapphire onto the flexible PI substrates using a wet transfer strategy ⁶⁸: First, a protective layer of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) has been spin-coated before releasing the MoS₂ film from the sapphire substrate in a potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution. The film has been scooped onto the pre-patterned polyimide substrate and dried, before removing the protective PMMA layer in acetone. The electrode areas have been defined by optical contact lithography, followed by tetrafluoromethane/oxygen (CF₄/O₂) reactive ion etching of the unprotected MoS₂ in the contact regions. Self-aligned side contacts of 50 nm of nickel (Ni) have then been sputter

deposited into the etched areas, followed by lift-off to form interdigitated drain-source electrodes. Finally, the photoactive MoS₂ channels have been patterned by CF₄/O₂ reactive ion etching with a photoresist mask, before the samples have been cleaned in acetone and isopropanol and softly blow-dried with nitrogen. A schematic of the complete fabrication process is shown in the supporting information in Figure S1.

Device characterization

The back-gated MSM MoS₂ photodetectors have been analyzed electro-optically with a Keithley SCS 4200 semiconductor analyzer in a multi-probe station with white LED (6500 K) illumination. Wavelength-dependent photocurrents were first amplified (FEMTO DLPCA-200) and then have been measured with lock-in technique at different monochromatic light wavelengths from 360 nm to 960 nm using a customized spectral response measurement set-up (see supporting information).

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

Brief explanation of the device fabrication process and of the customized monochromatic light setup. (PDF)

Acknowledgements

We thank Olof Engström and Zhenxing Wang (AMO GmbH) for fruitful discussions and Martin Otto (AMO GmbH) for atomic force microscopy. This work was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements 829035 (QUEFORMAL), 785219 and 881603 (Graphene Flagship), the European Regional Funds Project HEA2D (NW-1-1-036), the German Research Foundation (DFG) Project MOSTFLEX (407080863), and the German Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) Project NeuroTec (16ES1134)".

References

- (1) Zou, X.; Wang, J.; Chiu, C.-H.; Wu, Y.; Xiao, X.; Jiang, C.; Wu, W.-W.; Mai, L.; Chen, T.; Li, J.; Ho, J. C.; Liao, L. Interface Engineering for High-Performance Top-Gated MoS₂ Field-Effect Transistors. *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, *26* (36), 6255–6261. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201402008>.
- (2) Wang, Y.; Kim, J. C.; Wu, R. J.; Martinez, J.; Song, X.; Yang, J.; Zhao, F.; Mkhoyan, A.; Jeong, H. Y.; Chhowalla, M. Van Der Waals Contacts between Three-Dimensional Metals and Two-Dimensional Semiconductors. *Nature* **2019**, *568* (7750), 70. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1052-3>.
- (3) Mak, K. F.; Lee, C.; Hone, J.; Shan, J.; Heinz, T. F. Atomically Thin MoS₂: A New Direct-Gap Semiconductor. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2010**, *105* (13). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.105.136805>.
- (4) Lee, C.; Yan, H.; Brus, L. E.; Heinz, T. F.; Hone, J.; Ryu, S. Anomalous Lattice Vibrations of Single- and Few-Layer MoS₂. *ACS Nano* **2010**, *4* (5), 2695–2700. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn1003937>.
- (5) Bernardi, M.; Palummo, M.; Grossman, J. C. Extraordinary Sunlight Absorption and One Nanometer Thick Photovoltaics Using Two-Dimensional Monolayer Materials. *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13* (8), 3664–3670. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl401544y>.
- (6) Bertolazzi, S.; Brivio, J.; Kis, A. Stretching and Breaking of Ultrathin MoS₂. *ACS Nano* **2011**, *5* (12), 9703–9709. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn203879f>.
- (7) Yu, W. J.; Liu, Y.; Zhou, H.; Yin, A.; Li, Z.; Huang, Y.; Duan, X. Highly Efficient Gate-Tunable Photocurrent Generation in Vertical Heterostructures of Layered Materials. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2013**, *8* (12), 952–958. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2013.219>.
- (8) Lee, C.-H.; Lee, G.-H.; van der Zande, A. M.; Chen, W.; Li, Y.; Han, M.; Cui, X.; Arefe, G.; Nuckolls, C.; Heinz, T. F.; Guo, J.; Hone, J.; Kim, P. Atomically Thin p–n Junctions with van Der Waals Heterointerfaces. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2014**, *9* (9), 676–681. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2014.150>.
- (9) Yim, C.; O'Brien, M.; McEvoy, N.; Riazimehr, S.; Schäfer-Eberwein, H.; Bablich, A.; Pawar, R.; Iannaccone, G.; Downing, C.; Fiori, G.; Lemme, M. C.; Duesberg, G. S. Heterojunction Hybrid Devices from Vapor Phase Grown MoS₂. *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4* (1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep05458>.

- (10) Lopez-Sanchez, O.; Lembke, D.; Kayci, M.; Radenovic, A.; Kis, A. Ultrasensitive Photodetectors Based on Monolayer MoS₂. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2013**, *8* (7), 497–501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2013.100>.
- (11) Lee, S.; Park, Y.; Yoo, G.; Heo, J. Wavelength-Selective Enhancement of Photo-Responsivity in Metal-Gated Multi-Layer MoS₂ Phototransistors. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2017**, *111* (22), 223106. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5003315>.
- (12) Zhang, W.; Huang, J.-K.; Chen, C.-H.; Chang, Y.-H.; Cheng, Y.-J.; Li, L.-J. High-Gain Phototransistors Based on a CVD MoS₂ Monolayer. *Adv. Mater.* **2013**, *25* (25), 3456–3461. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201301244>.
- (13) Kufer, D.; Konstantatos, G. Highly Sensitive, Encapsulated MoS₂ Photodetector with Gate Controllable Gain and Speed. *Nano Lett.* **2015**, *15* (11), 7307–7313. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.5b02559>.
- (14) Lee, Y. T.; Kang, J.-H.; Kwak, K.; Ahn, J.; Choi, H. T.; Ju, B.-K.; Shokouh, S. H.; Im, S.; Park, M.-C.; Hwang, D. K. High-Performance 2D MoS₂ Phototransistor for Photo Logic Gate and Image Sensor. *ACS Photonics* **2018**, *5* (12), 4745–4750. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsp Photonics.8b01049>.
- (15) Marin, J. F. G.; Unuchek, D.; Watanabe, K.; Taniguchi, T.; Kis, A. MoS₂ Photodetectors Integrated with Photonic Circuits. *Npj 2D Mater. Appl.* **2019**, *3* (1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41699-019-0096-4>.
- (16) Castellanos-Gomez, A.; Buscema, M.; Molenaar, R.; Singh, V.; Janssen, L.; van der Zant, H. S. J.; Steele, G. A. Deterministic Transfer of Two-Dimensional Materials by All-Dry Viscoelastic Stamping. *2D Mater.* **2014**, *1* (1), 011002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1583/1/1/011002>.
- (17) Kim, D.-H.; Lu, N.; Ma, R.; Kim, Y.-S.; Kim, R.-H.; Wang, S.; Wu, J.; Won, S. M.; Tao, H.; Islam, A.; Yu, K. J.; Kim, T. -i.; Chowdhury, R.; Ying, M.; Xu, L.; Li, M.; Chung, H.-J.; Keum, H.; McCormick, M.; Liu, P.; Zhang, Y.-W.; Omenetto, F. G.; Huang, Y.; Coleman, T.; Rogers, J. A. Epidermal Electronics. *Science* **2011**, *333* (6044), 838–843. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1206157>.
- (18) Akinwande, D.; Petrone, N.; Hone, J. Two-Dimensional Flexible Nanoelectronics. *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 5678. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6678>.
- (19) Ko, H. C.; Stoykovich, M. P.; Song, J.; Malyarchuk, V.; Choi, W. M.; Yu, C.-J.; Geddes III, J. B.; Xiao, J.; Wang, S.; Huang, Y.; Rogers, J. A. A Hemispherical Electronic Eye Camera Based on Compressible Silicon Optoelectronics. *Nature* **2008**, *454* (7205), 748–753. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature07113>.
- (20) Lee, S.; Jung, S. W.; Park, S.; Ahn, J.; Hong, S. J.; Yoo, H. J.; Lee, M. H.; Cho, D.-I. Ultra-High Responsivity, Silicon Nanowire Photodetectors for Retinal Prosthesis; IEEE, 2012; pp 1364–1367. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MEMSYS.2012.6170420>.
- (21) Kataria, S.; Wagner, S.; Cusati, T.; Fortunelli, A.; Iannaccone, G.; Pandey, H.; Fiori, G.; Lemme, M. C. Growth-Induced Strain in Chemical Vapor Deposited Monolayer MoS₂: Experimental and Theoretical Investigation. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *4* (17), 1700031. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.201700031>.
- (22) Valdivia, A.; Tweet, D. J.; Conley, J. F. Atomic Layer Deposition of Two Dimensional MoS₂ on 150 Mm Substrates. *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. Vac. Surf. Films* **2016**, *34* (2), 021515. <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.4941245>.

- (23) Tao, L.; Chen, K.; Chen, Z.; Chen, W.; Gui, X.; Chen, H.; Li, X.; Xu, J.-B. Centimeter-Scale CVD Growth of Highly Crystalline Single-Layer MoS₂ Film with Spatial Homogeneity and the Visualization of Grain Boundaries. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9* (13), 12073–12081. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b00420>.
- (24) Lee, K.; Gatensby, R.; McEvoy, N.; Hallam, T.; Duesberg, G. S. High-Performance Sensors Based on Molybdenum Disulfide Thin Films. *Adv. Mater.* **2013**, *25* (46), 6699–6702. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201303230>.
- (25) Zhan, Y.; Liu, Z.; Najmaei, S.; Ajayan, P. M.; Lou, J. Large-Area Vapor-Phase Growth and Characterization of MoS₂ Atomic Layers on a SiO₂ Substrate. *Small* **2012**, *8* (7), 966–971. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.201102654>.
- (26) Zhang, J.; Yu, H.; Chen, W.; Tian, X.; Liu, D.; Cheng, M.; Xie, G.; Yang, W.; Yang, R.; Bai, X.; Shi, D.; Zhang, G. Scalable Growth of High-Quality Polycrystalline MoS₂ Monolayers on SiO₂ with Tunable Grain Sizes. *ACS Nano* **2014**, *8* (6), 6024–6030. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn5020819>.
- (27) Belete, M.; Kataria, S.; Turfanda, A.; Vaziri, S.; Wahlbrink, T.; Engström, O.; Lemme, M. C. Nonvolatile Resistive Switching in Nanocrystalline Molybdenum Disulfide with Ion-Based Plasticity. *Adv. Electron. Mater.* **2020**, 1900892. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aelm.201900892>.
- (28) Grundmann, A.; Andrzejewski, D.; Kümmell, T.; Bacher, G.; Heuken, M.; Kalisch, H.; Vescan, A. H₂S-Free Metal-Organic Vapor Phase Epitaxy of Coalesced 2D WS₂ Layers on Sapphire. *MRS Adv.* **2019**, *4* (10), 593–599. <https://doi.org/10.1557/adv.2018.669>.
- (29) Marx, M.; Nordmann, S.; Knoch, J.; Franzen, C.; Stampfer, C.; Andrzejewski, D.; Kümmell, T.; Bacher, G.; Heuken, M.; Kalisch, H.; Vescan, A. Large-Area MoS₂ Deposition via MOVPE. *J. Cryst. Growth* **2017**, *464*, 100–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrysgro.2016.11.020>.
- (30) Marx, M.; Grundmann, A.; Lin, Y.-R.; Andrzejewski, D.; Kümmell, T.; Bacher, G.; Heuken, M.; Kalisch, H.; Vescan, A. Metalorganic Vapor-Phase Epitaxy Growth Parameters for Two-Dimensional MoS₂. *J. Electron. Mater.* **2018**, *47* (2), 910–916. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11664-017-5937-3>.
- (31) Splendiani, A.; Sun, L.; Zhang, Y.; Li, T.; Kim, J.; Chim, C.-Y.; Galli, G.; Wang, F. Emerging Photoluminescence in Monolayer MoS₂. *Nano Lett.* **2010**, *10* (4), 1271–1275. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl903868w>.
- (32) Buscema, M.; Steele, G. A.; van der Zant, H. S. J.; Castellanos-Gomez, A. The Effect of the Substrate on the Raman and Photoluminescence Emission of Single-Layer MoS₂. *Nano Res.* **2014**, *7* (4), 561–571. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-014-0424-0>.
- (33) Castellanos-Gomez, A.; Quereda, J.; Meulen, H. P. van der; Agraït, N.; Rubio-Bollinger, G. Spatially Resolved Optical Absorption Spectroscopy of Single- and Few-Layer MoS₂ by Hyperspectral Imaging. *Nanotechnology* **2016**, *27* (11), 115705. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/27/11/115705>.
- (34) Li, H.; Zhang, Q.; Yap, C. C. R.; Tay, B. K.; Edwin, T. H. T.; Olivier, A.; Baillargeat, D. From Bulk to Monolayer MoS₂: Evolution of Raman Scattering. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2012**, *22* (7), 1385–1390. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201102111>.
- (35) Riazimehr, S.; Kataria, S.; Gonzalez-Medina, J. M.; Wagner, S.; Shaygan, M.; Suckow, S.; Ruiz, F. G.; Engström, O.; Godoy, A.; Lemme, M. C. High Responsivity and Quantum Efficiency of Graphene/Silicon Photodiodes Achieved by Interdigitating Schottky and Gated Regions. *ACS Photonics* **2019**, *6* (1), 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsphotonics.8b00951>.

- (36) Schneider, D. S.; Bablich, A.; Lemme, M. C. Flexible Hybrid Graphene/a-Si:H Multispectral Photodetectors. *Nanoscale* **2017**, *9* (25), 8573–8579. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7NR02828H>.
- (37) Shaygan, M.; Otto, M.; Sagade, A. A.; Chavarin, C. A.; Bacher, G.; Mertin, W.; Neumaier, D. Low Resistive Edge Contacts to CVD-Grown Graphene Using a CMOS Compatible Metal. *Ann. Phys.* **2017**, *529* (11), 1600410. <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.201600410>.
- (38) Jain, A.; Szabó, Á.; Parzefall, M.; Bonvin, E.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Bharadwaj, P.; Luisier, M.; Novotny, L. One-Dimensional Edge Contacts to a Monolayer Semiconductor. *Nano Lett.* **2019**, *19* (10), 6914–6923. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.9b02166>.
- (39) Cheng, Z.; Yu, Y.; Singh, S.; Price, K.; Noyce, S. G.; Lin, Y.-C.; Cao, L.; Franklin, A. D. Immunity to Contact Scaling in MoS₂ Transistors Using in Situ Edge Contacts. *Nano Lett.* **2019**. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.9b01355>.
- (40) Han, P.; Marie, L. S.; Wang, Q. X.; Quirk, N.; Fatimy, A. E.; Ishigami, M.; Barbara, P. Highly Sensitive MoS₂ Photodetectors with Graphene Contacts. *Nanotechnology* **2018**, *29* (20), 20LT01. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/aab4bb>.
- (41) Radisavljevic, B.; Radenovic, A.; Brivio, J.; Giacometti, V.; Kis, A. Single-Layer MoS₂ Transistors. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2011**, *6* (3), 147–150. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2010.279>.
- (42) Xie, L.; Liao, M.; Wang, S.; Yu, H.; Du, L.; Tang, J.; Zhao, J.; Zhang, J.; Chen, P.; Lu, X.; Wang, G.; Xie, G.; Yang, R.; Shi, D.; Zhang, G. Graphene-Contacted Ultrashort Channel Monolayer MoS₂ Transistors. *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29* (37), 1702522. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201702522>.
- (43) Buscema, M.; O. Island, J.; J. Groenendijk, D.; I. Blanter, S.; A. Steele, G.; Zant, H. S. J. van der; Castellanos-Gomez, A. Photocurrent Generation with Two-Dimensional van Der Waals Semiconductors. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2015**, *44* (11), 3691–3718. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5CS00106D>.
- (44) Bartolomeo, A. D.; Genovese, L.; Foller, T.; Giubileo, F.; Luongo, G.; Croin, L.; Liang, S.-J.; Ang, L. K.; Schleberger, M. Electrical Transport and Persistent Photoconductivity in Monolayer MoS₂ phototransistors. *Nanotechnology* **2017**, *28* (21), 214002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/aa6d98>.
- (45) Tu, L.; Cao, R.; Wang, X.; Chen, Y.; Wu, S.; Wang, F.; Wang, Z.; Shen, H.; Lin, T.; Zhou, P.; Meng, X.; Hu, W.; Liu, Q.; Wang, J.; Liu, M.; Chu, J. Ultrasensitive Negative Capacitance Phototransistors. *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, *11* (1), 101. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13769-z>.
- (46) Vaziri, S.; Ostling, M.; Lemme, M. C. A Hysteresis-Free High-k Dielectric and Contact Resistance Considerations for Graphene Field Effect Transistors. *ECS Trans.* **2011**, *41*, 165–171.
- (47) Bittle, E. G.; Basham, J. I.; Jackson, T. N.; Jurchescu, O. D.; Gundlach, D. J. Mobility Overestimation Due to Gated Contacts in Organic Field-Effect Transistors. *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, *7* (1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10908>.
- (48) Das, S.; Chen, H.-Y.; Penumatcha, A. V.; Appenzeller, J. High Performance Multilayer MoS₂ Transistors with Scandium Contacts. *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13* (1), 100–105. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl303583v>.
- (49) Park, J.; Park, Y.; Yoo, G.; Heo, J. Bias-Dependent Photoresponsivity of Multi-Layer MoS₂ Phototransistors. *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **2017**, *12* (1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11671-017-2368-2>.
- (50) Furchi, M. M.; Polyushkin, D. K.; Pospischil, A.; Mueller, T. Mechanisms of Photoconductivity in Atomically Thin MoS₂. *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14* (11), 6165–6170. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl502339q>.

- (51) Saenz, G. A.; Karapetrov, G.; Curtis, J.; Kaul, A. B. Ultra-High Photoresponsivity in Suspended Metal-Semiconductor-Metal Mesoscopic Multilayer MoS₂ Broadband Detector from UV-to-IR with Low Schottky Barrier Contacts. *Sci. Rep.* **2018**, *8* (1), 1276. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-19367-1>.
- (52) Lee, S.; Park, J.; Yun, Y.; Lee, J.; Heo, J. Enhanced Photoresponsivity of Multilayer MoS₂ Phototransistor Using Localized Au Schottky Junction Formed by Spherical-Lens Photolithography. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* *0* (0), 1900053. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.201900053>.
- (53) Gong, X.; Tong, M.; Xia, Y.; Cai, W.; Moon, J. S.; Cao, Y.; Yu, G.; Shieh, C.-L.; Nilsson, B.; Heeger, A. J. High-Detectivity Polymer Photodetectors with Spectral Response from 300 Nm to 1450 Nm. *Science* **2009**, *325* (5948), 1665–1667.
- (54) Choi, W.; Cho, M. Y.; Konar, A.; Lee, J. H.; Cha, G.-B.; Hong, S. C.; Kim, S.; Kim, J.; Jena, D.; Joo, J.; Kim, S. High-Detectivity Multilayer MoS₂ Phototransistors with Spectral Response from Ultraviolet to Infrared. *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, *24* (43), 5832–5836. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201201909>.
- (55) Najmaei, S.; Liu, Z.; Zhou, W.; Zou, X.; Shi, G.; Lei, S.; Yakobson, B. I.; Idrobo, J.-C.; Ajayan, P. M.; Lou, J. Vapour Phase Growth and Grain Boundary Structure of Molybdenum Disulphide Atomic Layers. *Nat. Mater.* **2013**, *12* (8), 754–759. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat3673>.
- (56) Sim, D. M.; Kim, M.; Yim, S.; Choi, M.-J.; Choi, J.; Yoo, S.; Jung, Y. S. Controlled Doping of Vacancy-Containing Few-Layer MoS₂ via Highly Stable Thiol-Based Molecular Chemisorption. *ACS Nano* **2015**, *9* (12), 12115–12123. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nano.5b05173>.
- (57) Park, Y.; Baac, H. W.; Heo, J.; Yoo, G. Thermally Activated Trap Charges Responsible for Hysteresis in Multilayer MoS₂ Field-Effect Transistors. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2016**, *108* (8), 083102. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4942406>.
- (58) Belete, M.; Kataria, S.; Koch, U.; Kruth, M.; Engelhard, C.; Mayer, J.; Engström, O.; Lemme, M. C. Dielectric Properties and Ion Transport in Layered MoS₂ Grown by Vapor-Phase Sulfurization for Potential Applications in Nanoelectronics. *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **2018**, *1* (11), 6197–6204. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.8b01412>.
- (59) Yang, M.; Kim, T.-Y.; Lee, T.; Hong, S. Nanoscale Enhancement of Photoconductivity by Localized Charge Traps in the Grain Structures of Monolayer MoS₂. *Sci. Rep.* **2018**, *8* (1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-34209-w>.
- (60) Amani, M.; Lien, D.-H.; Kiriya, D.; Xiao, J.; Azcatl, A.; Noh, J.; Madhupathy, S. R.; Addou, R.; Kc, S.; Dubey, M.; Cho, K.; Wallace, R. M.; Lee, S.-C.; He, J.-H.; Ager, J. W.; Zhang, X.; Yablonovitch, E.; Javey, A. Near-Unity Photoluminescence Quantum Yield in MoS₂. *Science* **2015**, *350* (6264), 1065–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad2114>.
- (61) Wang, X.; Wang, P.; Wang, J.; Hu, W.; Zhou, X.; Guo, N.; Huang, H.; Sun, S.; Shen, H.; Lin, T.; Tang, M.; Liao, L.; Jiang, A.; Sun, J.; Meng, X.; Chen, X.; Lu, W.; Chu, J. Ultrasensitive and Broadband MoS₂ Photodetector Driven by Ferroelectrics. *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27* (42), 6575–6581. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201503340>.
- (62) Kozawa, D.; Kumar, R.; Carvalho, A.; Kumar Amara, K.; Zhao, W.; Wang, S.; Toh, M.; Ribeiro, R. M.; Castro Neto, A. H.; Matsuda, K.; Eda, G. Photocarrier Relaxation Pathway in Two-Dimensional Semiconducting Transition Metal Dichalcogenides. *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 4543. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms5543>.
- (63) Carvalho, A.; Ribeiro, R. M.; Castro Neto, A. H. Band Nesting and the Optical Response of Two-

Dimensional Semiconducting Transition Metal Dichalcogenides. *Phys. Rev. B* **2013**, 88 (11), 115205. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.88.115205>.

(64) Algreve, P. V.; Marshall, J.; Seregard, S. Age-Related Maculopathy and the Impact of Blue Light Hazard: Acta Ophthalmologica Scandinavica 2006. *Acta Ophthalmol. Scand.* **2006**, 84 (1), 4–15. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0420.2005.00627.x>.

(65) Burkhard, G. F.; Hoke, E. T.; McGehee, M. D. Accounting for Interference, Scattering, and Electrode Absorption to Make Accurate Internal Quantum Efficiency Measurements in Organic and Other Thin Solar Cells. *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, 22 (30), 3293–3297. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201000883>.

(66) Beal, A. R.; Hughes, H. P. Kramers-Kronig Analysis of the Reflectivity Spectra of 2H-MoS₂, 2H-MoSe₂ and 2H-MoTe₂. *J. Phys. C Solid State Phys.* **1979**, 12 (5), 881. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3719/12/5/017>.

(67) Jen, S.-H.; Bertrand, J. A.; George, S. M. Critical Tensile and Compressive Strains for Cracking of Al₂O₃ Films Grown by Atomic Layer Deposition. *J. Appl. Phys.* **2011**, 109 (8), 084305. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3567912>.

(68) Wagner, S.; Weisenstein, C.; Smith, A. D.; Östling, M.; Kataria, S.; Lemme, M. C. Graphene Transfer Methods for the Fabrication of Membrane-Based NEMS Devices. *Microelectron. Eng.* **2016**, 159, 108–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mee.2016.02.065>.